

Chemical Investigation of *Solanum nigrum* Berries

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The various parts of *Solanum* species have been studied in the past and found to be a rich source of steroidal alkaloids and is extensively used in Indian system of medicine¹. A review of the literature showed that *Solanum nigrum* berries from New Zealand have earlier been studied and found to contain four steroidal alkaloid glycosides, solamargine, solasonin, α - and β -solanigrin, all of which yield solasodine as the aglycone². Recently Varshney and Sharma³ have reported the presence of a steroidal sapogenin, tigogenin in the form of saponin in *Solanum nigrum* berries from Uttar Pradesh. But no work has been carried out on the alkaloids of these berries from India.

The well defatted powder of berries of *Solanum nigrum* obtained locally was exhausted with ethanol giving a dark green coloured gummy mass which was extracted with 5% acetic acid, filtered and the filtrate was heated upto 30° on water bath⁴, addition of ammonium hydroxide (conc.) precipitated the basic glycosides. This was purified by dissolution in 5% acetic acid and reprecipitation with ammonium hydroxide several times till light coloured precipitate was obtained which on TLC showed the presence of three steroidal alkaloids.

The mixture of steroidal alkaloid glycosides obtained was hydrolysed with 5N methanolic hydrochloric acid and the aglycone hydrochloride separated as needles, which were refluxed with ammonium hydroxide (conc.) for 1 hr, liberating the aglycone. The aglycone on TLC showed the presence of two aglycones.

The aglycones were separated by column chromatography on alumina (Brockmann) to give two separate pure products. The product A on crystallisation with methanol acetone mixture yielded colourless needles, m.p. 194–96°, acetate m.p. 160–62° (cf. solasodine m.p. 198–200°, acetate m.p. 165–66°). It has been identified as solasodine by mixed m.p. and TLC with authentic sample. The product B on crystallisation from methanol chloroform mixture yielded colourless shiny plates m.p. 166–67°. All attempts to form an acetate were unsuccessful. It has been identified as solasodiene⁵ (cf. solasodiene m.p. 168–70°).

The ammoniacal filtrate from alkaloid glycoside precipitation was extracted with water saturated *n*-butanol and on concentration gave a brownish gummy product giving all the tests for saponins. It was hydrolysed with 7% sulphuric acid in the usual manner giving

1. K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, *Indian Medicinal Plants*, Vol. III, IInd Edition, p. 1752–54.
2. L. H. Briggs, R. C. Cambie and J. C. Hoare, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4645.
3. I. P. Varshney and S. C. Sharma, *Phytochemistry*, 1965, **4**, 967-8.
4. R. Kuhn and I. Low, *Chem. Ber.*, 1955, **88**, 289.
5. H. Sender, *Naturwiss*, 1961, **48**, 303–04.

mixture of aglycones which on TLC showed the presence of 3 sapogenins which were separated into three different pure products by column chromatography on alumina (Brockmann). The product (i) colourless crystals m.p. 199–201°, acetate m.p. 187–88° (cf. diosgenin m.p. 204–07°, acetate m.p. 190°). The product (ii) colourless needles, m.p. 205–06°, acetate m.p. 200–01° (cf. tigogenin m.p. 206–07°, acetate m.p. 200–02°), these have been identified as diosgenin and tigogenin respectively by mixed m.p., TLC and I.R. spectrum with authentic samples. The product (iii) is present in traces and could not be worked further due to the paucity of material.

The occurrence of diosgenin with solasodine provokes an interesting speculation to the possible mode of biogenesis of solasodine. This is somewhat proved by Briggs and Shea⁶ by heating *o*-nitro-solasodine with aqueous acetic acid yielding diosgenin in small amounts and an isomer of diosgenin was their main product. It may be possible that the two genins found in this plant may be transformation products of the solasodine or *vice versa* and to prove this further work is in progress.

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6. L. H. Briggs and O. Shea, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1654.